

Moderating Effect of the Economy on Fiscal Management in Local Government in Nigeria, 1993-2016

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Abstract

This study examines the moderating influence of the economy on the nexus between local government expenditure and revenue in Nigeria. Data on local government expenditure and revenue and gross domestic product were collected from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletins covering a period of 24 years (1993–2016). The data were log normalized in order to eliminate heteroskedasticity. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data. The results indicate that gross domestic product has a significant positive influence on local government expenditure and revenue. Also, the results show that the local government revenue has a significant positive effect on local government expenditure in Nigeria. The study therefore concludes that the Nigerian economy has a significant effect on fiscal management in local government. The study recommends among others that state and federal government should take measures to improve the economy since it has significant positive effect on local government fiscal management.

Keywords: economy, fiscal management, local government.

1. Introduction

The local government system is designed to deliver public goods to local areas and their environs. This is possible through local government expenditure framework. This framework works through the annual budgetary system, which is funded through allocation from the federation account, 10 per cent of state internally generated revenue and local government own-internally generated revenue. This is to suggest that the local government expenditure system depends largely on the availability of revenue. Interestingly, however, how much revenue is available to the local government system is a function of the health of the economy, which is measured statistically by gross domestic product.

Gross domestic product (GDP) is the sum naira value of all the goods and services produced in Nigeria, measured usually over a year. Countries are traditionally ranked using the value of their gross domestic product. For example, while USA, China, Japan and Germany are ranked numbers 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively; Nigeria is ranked 22. Gross domestic product is a good measure of economic growth. However, it does not tell about economic development (level of poverty, level of unemployment and the gap between the rich and the poor), which is perhaps a more important or useful measure of human life.

Fiscal management in local government has not received the attention it deserves from scholars and practitioners despite the strategic role of local government system in Nigeria. Few of the studies concentrate scholarly efforts in examining the challenges and

prospects of financial management in local government. It is in view of this that this study examines the influence of the economy on fiscal management in local government in Nigeria. The study further examines the effect of local government revenue and the economy on local government expenditure in Nigeria. In view of this, the study tests the following hypotheses:

H₁: Local government revenue has no significant effect on local government expenditure in Nigeria.

H₂: Gross domestic product has no significant effect on local government expenditure in Nigeria.

This study is significant in many respects. First, it contributes to understanding of concepts, theories, empirics and methodology as they relates to fiscal management in local government. Also, local government councils, state governments and federal government stand to benefit from the results of the study. This is particularly true since the local government system is the closest to the local people and it is very strategic to even national development. The remaining part of the study is divided into literature review, methodology, results and discussion and conclusion and recommendations.

2. Literature Review

Ojo (2009) examines the efficiency of financial management in local governments in Nigeria. The study articulates the instruments that will help the local government councils to manage their funds adequately and be able to perform their statutory duties accordingly. Specifically, the study discusses the various tools and techniques of efficient financial management which could assist the local government with performing their roles. These include the use of budget, rational approach, incremental approach, zero-based budgeting approach, planning, programming and budgeting system, audit alarm, and auditing approach. The study concludes that a thorough adoption and application of these approaches will improve financial management of local governments in Nigeria and enhance the quality of service delivery at the grass root.

Odd-Hedge, Lucas, Jamal and Erasto (2010) examine the capacity of local governments in Tanzania with respect to financial management and revenue enhancement and analyzes trends in financial accountability and efficiency for the period 2000-2007. Data were collected using a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods, including surveys. The study concludes that the process of decentralization in local government has contributed to improving the capacity of local government in financial management. Coker and Adams (2012) examine the challenges of managing local government finance in Nigeria. They focus on how local government councils manage their finances against the background of lack of financial autonomy, corruption, and, undue interference in local affairs, especially in the areas of operation of joint state-local government accounts which gives the state government undue advantage over local governments. The methodology used in the study was descriptive qualitative analysis. The findings show that local governments in Nigeria have not been doing well due to lack of financial autonomy, undue meddlesomeness of state governments in local affairs, corruption among local government officials.

Eze and Harrison (2013) examine financial management systems in the local governments in Nigeria. They primarily evaluated the roles, powers and challenges of the treasury department of local government in Nigeria. Results revealed that lack of adequate technical capacity and constitutional loopholes associated with the creation of the state and local government joint accounts are the key factors affecting efficient financial management in the local government. They recommend that financial autonomy and improved technical capacity of treasury department of local government would promote sound financial management in the local government. Also, Izueke, Anyadike and Nzekwe (2013) examine the management of local government finance in Nigeria with particular interest on the challenges and prospects. The study examines measurable instruments and conditions for effective management of finance for this level of government. The methodology used in the study was descriptive qualitative analysis. The management of local government finance was analyzed using efficiency theory. It was discovered that management of local government finance in Nigeria has been bedeviled by lack of long-term financial planning, corruption, the use of inappropriate budgetary system.

Furthermore, Salahu (2013) investigates local government fiscal management and intergovernmental fiscal relations. The study equally reviews statutory allocations and internally generated revenue of the selected local governments. The study adopts the use of questionnaires to elicit data on the perceptions of local residents on the level of local government performance. Result shows that a strong approach to expand the scope of local autonomy will have to come through a corresponding expansion in IGR mobilization, which implies that when local government assumes a level of fiscal self-reliance, autonomy expands and performance level begins to appreciate.

Murana (2015) examines local government finance in Nigeria using Iwo Local Government as a Case Study. Data for the study were gathered from face-to-face interview and available records in Iwo Local Government. The data collected were subjected to descriptive statistics and content analysis. The study explores various sources of financing local governments in Nigeria. It also explains the financial relationship of Nigerian local government vis-à-vis State and Federal Government using theory of decentralization. Result shows that financial transfers from federal government (Statutory Federal Allocation) are the most viable and reliable source of local government revenue.

Oluwafemi and Tolu (2016) examine fiscal accountability and resource management and their implication on sustainable development. The study employs the use of secondary data to source its information. The study observes that lack of fiscal accountability and resource management are basically responsible for poor governance in Nigeria. The study posits that effective management and financial accountability should be encouraged in local government service to enable the country achieve a reasonable level of development.

3. Methodology

This study adopts time series research design. Data on local government expenditure and revenue and gross domestic product were extracted from the Central Bank of Nigeria

Statistical Bulletins (1993-2016). The data were log normalized to remove the presence of heteroskedasticity. Descriptive (mean, standard error, standard deviation, range, minimum and maximum) and inferential statistics (correlation and regression analysis) were used to analyze the data. The study estimated and tested the following model:

$$\log \text{exp}_t = \alpha + \beta_1 \log \text{rev}_t + \beta_2 \log \text{gdp}_t + \varepsilon_t$$

Whereas:

$\log \text{exp}$ = local government expenditure at year t log normalized to eliminate presence of heteroskedasticity.

$\log \text{rev}$ = local government revenue at year t log normalized to eliminate presence of heteroskedasticity.

$\log \text{gdp}$ = Gross Domestic Product at year t log normalized to eliminate presence of heteroskedasticity.

α = Constant, which is the value of the dependent variable assuming that all the explanatory variables are 0.

$\beta_1 - \beta_2$ = Beta coefficients of the explanatory variables.

ε = Stochastic error term

t = Year subscript (in this case, $t = 24$ years)

4. Results and Discussion

The results of descriptive statistics are reported in Table 1.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics

<i>Summary Statistics</i>	<i>logexp</i>	<i>logrev</i>	<i>loggdp</i>
Mean	5.508	5.658	9.547
Standard Error	0.321	0.340	0.280
Median	5.956	6.271	9.466
Standard Deviation	1.573	1.665	1.372
Sample Variance	2.473	2.771	1.882
Kurtosis	-1.259	-1.351	-1.023
Skewness	-0.541	-0.528	-0.068
Range	4.324	4.545	4.534
Minimum	2.943	2.956	6.994
Maximum	7.267	7.501	11.528
Sum	132.198	135.785	229.131
Count	24	24	24

Source: MS Excel 2007 Outputs

It is important to note that the figures in Table 1 are log normalized values of the data set of the study. From Table 1, the mean statistic values of variables of interest are local government expenditure (5.5082426), local government revenue (5.65769) and gross domestic product (9.547128). As expected, the expenditure of the local governments is lower than the value of the gross domestic product of the country. This is

true since the local government system is a subset of the national economy. Also, it is important to observe that the mean value of local government revenue is higher than the mean value of local government expenditure, suggesting that between 1993 and 2016, the local governments in Nigeria recorded a surplus.

Similarly, the standard deviation statistic values of variables of interest are local government expenditure (1.5726789), local government revenue (1.664744) and gross domestic product (1.3718715). These results suggest that in terms of variability or volatility, local government revenue is more volatile (unstable) than local government expenditure and gross domestic product. Table 1 also shows that the minimum statistic values of the variables of interest are local government expenditure (2.9428588), local government revenue (2.956472) and gross domestic product (6.9936394). In the same vein, the maximum statistic values of the variables of interest are local government expenditure (7.2669042), local government revenue (7.50111) and gross domestic product (11.527711).

Furthermore, the count values in Table 1 show that the data set covers a period of 24 years. The range values are obtained as the difference between maximum mean and minimum mean for each of the variable of the study. The values of the standard error for the variables suggest that local government revenue has a higher spread (0.3210217) than local government expenditure (0.339815) and gross domestic product (0.2800321). The statistic values of Kurtosis and Skewness are less than 3.0, which suggest clearly that the residual values of the data are not normally distributed. In order to confirm this normality test result, the Shapiro Wilk test for normal data was carried out and it shows the results in Table 2.

Table 2

Shapiro Wilk W Test for Normal Data

Variable	Obs	W	V	z	Prob>z
logexp	24	0.86751	3.574	2.597	0.00470
logrev	24	0.85794	3.832	2.739	0.00308
loggdp	24	0.94596	1.458	0.768	0.22115

Source: STATA 13 Outputs

As shown in Table 2, the prob > z values of logexp and logrev are significant at 5% level of significance, that is, they are less than 0.05, which means that they are not normally distributed. However, loggdp is normally distributed with prob > z greater than 0.05. The overall net result of the normality test shows that the residual of the data set is not normally distributed.

The results of correlation analysis are reported in Table 3. Correlation analysis measures the degree of association between two variables of interest.

Table 3

Correlation Matrix

Variable	logexp	logrev	loggdp
logexp	1.0000	0.9952	0.9457
		0.0000	0.0000
logrev		1.0000	0.9368
			0.0000

loggdp

1.0000

Source: STATA 13 Outputs

As shown in Table 3, the association between local government expenditure and revenue is statistically significant and positive ($\beta = 0.9952$, sig-value = 0.0000). Similarly, the association between local government and gross domestic product is statistically significant and positive ($\beta = 0.9457$, sig-value = 0.0000). Also, the association between local government revenue and gross domestic product is significant and positive ($\beta = 0.9368$, sig-value = 0.0000).

Furthermore, in order to establish the appropriate regression analysis that fits the data set of the study, heteroskedasticity test was carried out and the results show $\chi^2(1) = 0.64$ and $\text{prob} > \chi^2 = 0.4238$, which clearly shows that there is absence of heteroskedasticity in the data set of the study since the value is not significant, that is, it is greater than 0.05. Having accounted for all the diagnostic tests, the results of regression analysis are reported in Table 4.

Table 4

Regression Results

logexp	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P>t	[95% Conf.	Interval]
logrev	.8433433	.0529169	15.94	0.000	.7332967	.95339
loggdp	.1254415	.0642138	1.95	0.064	-.0080984	.2589813
__cons	-.4607383	.3499813	-1.32	0.202	-1.188564	.2670877

Source: STATA 13 Outputs

As shown in Table 4, local government revenue has significant positive effect on local government expenditure ($\beta = .8433433$, t-value = 15.94, p-value = 0.000). Similarly, gross domestic product shows significant (at 10 per cent) positive effect on local government expenditure ($\beta = .1254415$, t-value = 1.95, p-value = 0.064). These results are in line with the a priori expectation, since it is not conceivable that revenue will have negative effect on expenditure.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examines the effect of the economy on fiscal management of local government in Nigeria. As expected, the gross domestic product shows higher mean than local government expenditure and revenue. However, local government revenue shows higher volatility or spread than local government expenditure and gross domestic product. Also, gross domestic product shows significant association with local government expenditure and revenue.

Similarly, local government revenue shows significant positive effect on local government expenditure and gross domestic product. In view of these results, the study recommends that measures should be taken to improve the gross domestic product of the country so as to enhance local government expenditure and revenue. Similarly, steps should be taken by state and federal government to ensure that revenue accruable to local government is enhanced since it shows significant positive effect on local government expenditure.

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